

Design and Development of Sugarcane Stripper Machine

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Abstract

Índía is the second-largest producer of sugarcane in the world. During 2018-19, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Punjab, and Bihar are Índian states that have produced maximum quantities of sugarcane. In 2019, approximately 307 lakh tonnes of sugarcane were produced in Índía, which is nearly 11.8 percent of the global sugarcane production. Sugarcane crop has very long leaves. Stripping of sugarcane leaves is a major problem, which requires labor-intensive effort. Therefore, to resolve this problem, a tractor-operated sugarcane stripper machine was designed using the Computer-aided Design (CAD) software. In the mainframe of CaD design, a power transmission system, transportation system, feed hopper conveyor, sugarcane de-topper, and a stripper system were designed. This machine will reduce human drudgery. Currently, this sugarcane stripper machine is getting very good acceptance nationwide. Further research has been undertaken at the Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, Sam Higgin bottom University of agriculture Technology and Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh Índía. This machine was designed. The use of this machine will also help in reducing the cost and time of operation. In the future, this machine will help in improving the quality of stripping as well as ensuring effective utilization of the resources. The Design and development of sugarcane leaf stripper machines will play a significant role.

Keywords: Tractor, Sugarcane, Stripper, Reduce human drudgery.

Introduction

agriculture is the only source of livelihood for about two-thirds of Índía's population. Índian agriculture contributes about 43 percent of the geographical area and about 16 percent of the GDP. The number of crops grown by farmers and includes different food crops. Sugarcane is one of the important commercial crops grown in Índía and plays a pivotal role in the national economy. Agricultural operations are facing serious challenges due to labor shortages, not only in peak working season but also in unusual times. It is a long-duration crop and requires around 10-18 months to mature depending on the geographical conditions. Índía is one of the largest sugarcane-producing countries in the world covering about 18.52 percent of the area and contributing to 18.45 percent of the world's sugarcane production. Uttar Pradesh is the largest sugarcane-producing state of Índía which accounts for 38.61 percent of the total sugarcane production as per 2013-14 data. The second and third largest

states are Maharashtra and Karnataka. Other major sugarcane-producing states of India include Bihar, Assam, Haryana, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh, and Tamil Nadu.

Sugarcane cultivation in India is a labor-intensive process. Farmers mainly depend on manpower and the cultivation of sugarcane requires constant participation of labor throughout the crop cycle. The labor shortage is often felt in the agricultural sector. For want of adequate labor at fair wages, most of the work operations are delayed, resulting in low production and productivity. It is estimated that 134 man-hours are required per metric ton of sugar produced. Of this, one-third is required for production while the remaining two-thirds is used for harvesting, peeling, cleaning, and loading. Therefore, the mechanization of sugarcane shredders is necessary not only to reduce the production cost but also to reduce the human accident involved in manual shredding operations and to ensure quality. The labor shortage is one of the reasons why many farmers have moved away from this crop. Mechanization is considered as an option to solve the problem of labor shortage.

New income generation opportunities need to be created through sugarcane. This will help in reducing the increasing production cost, procuring costly inputs from the market, and making the plant and plantation system sustainable. Raises the socio-economic status of small and marginal resource farmers and generates employment especially for rural women and youth. About 80 percent of the world's sugar is produced from sugarcane in tropical and subtropical climates, with the remaining 20 percent from sugar beet, which is grown mostly in temperate regions of the Northern Hemisphere. For sugarcane, agricultural activities like transplanting, inter-culture, harvesting, leaf removal, congratulation, loading, etc. come. Farmers require maximum labor force; sufficient funds and it is a more time-consuming process. In the process of harvesting, peeling, and transporting sugarcane, we face various problems and these are not easily solved.

Material and method

Uttar Pradesh is the major state of sugarcane production. Sugarcane harvesting operation involves harvesting, shredding, and transporting sugarcane as it requires huge energy. The methods of shoveling sugarcane in Uttar Pradesh are mainly manual. The design and development of stripper for sugarcane removing is being done at Sam Higginbottom University of Agricultural Technology and Sciences, Division of Agricultural Engineering, Prayagraj district of Uttar Pradesh.

Components of sugarcane stripper

The following parts of tractor operated stripper machine are frame, hopper, stripper roller, spring loaded roller and air blower etc.

Fig. 1 Component of sugarcane stripper

Manual sugarcane shredder

In Uttar Pradesh, the removal of leaves is carried out using locally operated hand tools or manually by hand. Farmers generally use sickles and knives of old designs made of iron for shredding sugarcane. Sugarcane harvesting includes harvesting, removing, and separating the upper (leaf) part of sugarcane, etc. The use of hand-operated machines is very dangerous and harmful for humans, which are not ergonomically good. Due to which the accidents caused by labor are more. Hence workers should use a stripper to shred sugarcane safely.

Sugarcane stripper

Sugarcane stripper has been developed for stripping leaves after harvesting sugarcane, which is used for PTO of tractors. Power-operated stripper machine. In this machine, after harvesting the sugarcane, the sugarcane is put in the stripper machine for stripping the leaves, like sugarcane is applied to extract the juice from the sugarcane. The peeling of the leaf is done by the rubber finger fitted in the machine. The machine is equipped with spring-loaded rollers at the front and back, which reduce the holding and sliding of the sugarcane and the air blower is installed at the top which reduces the removal of leaves. With this machine, labor accidents can be reduced, and leaf peeling can be done in less time. This machine can be easily carried from one place to another. It will prove to be very useful for the farmers.

Sugarcane stripping capacity

To find the field capacity of sugarcane, the total area involved in the operation which is the total time taken in shaving was already noted during both mechanical and manual shredding trials. The field capacity is obtained by dividing the area involved in the peeling operation by the total time taken for peeling in both mechanical and manual tests.

Cost calculation

On the basis of shoveling by mechanical method, the total shaving cost includes machine cost, labor cost, and loading and transportation of sugarcane. The cost of manual sugarcane shredder includes labor cost and loading and transportation of sugarcane. Transportation costs may vary with the distance of the industry from the region. Total crop cost on sugarcane shellings Rs. = Sugarcane harvesting + Sugarcane shellings + Transportation cost + Labor cost, etc.

Conclusion

Mechanization of sugarcane husks is essential not only to reduce the production cost, but also to reduce accidents in manual harvesting operations, and to ensure quality yield. The manual and mechanical stripper was evaluated to know its performance. The study shows time to harvest, field capacity, and total cost of sugarcane are concluded as follows.

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